

The bisphenol A metabolite MBP causes proteome alterations in male *Cyprinodon variegatus* fish characteristic of estrogenic endocrine disruption[☆]

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ABSTRACT

The toxicological status of bisphenol A (BPA) is under strong debate. Whereas in vitro it is an agonist of the estrogen receptor with a potency ca. 10^5 -fold lower than the natural female hormone estradiol, in vivo exposure causes only mild effects at concentration thresholds environmentally not relevant and inconsistent among species. By using a proteomic approach, shotgun liver proteome analysis, we show that 7-d exposure to 10 µg/L of the BPA metabolite, 4-methyl-2,4-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)pent-1-ene (MBP), and not the same exposure to the parental molecule BPA, alters the liver proteome of male *Cyprinodon variegatus* fish. Different physiological and environmental conditions leading to biotransformation of BPA to MBP may partly explain the conflicting results so far reported for in vivo BPA exposures. The pattern of alteration induced by MBP is similar to that caused by estradiol, and indicative of estrogenic endocrine disruption. MBP enhanced ribosomal activity, protein synthesis and transport, with upregulation of 91% of the ribosome-related proteins, and 12 proteins whose expression is regulated by estrogen-responsive elements, including vitellogenin and zona pellucida. Whey acidic protein (WAP) was the protein most affected by MBP exposure (FC = 68). This result points at WAP as novel biomarker for xenoestrogens.

1. Introduction

Xenoestrogens are synthetic chemicals that bind to specific estrogen receptors (ER) and induce biological responses similar to those of estradiol, although at concentrations generally 3 to 6 orders of magnitude higher (Witorsch, 2002). In vitro tests, such as those using recombinant yeast, detect molecules that bind to ER, and thus with potential for estrogenic endocrine disruption (ED). These binding assays quantify the affinity of a suspected xenoestrogen by the ER. However, ligand:ER interaction per se does not predict the final biological effects, which depend on downstream processes, including migration of the ligand:ER complex to the nucleus and binding to a promoting region of several genes, termed estrogen responsive element (ERE), which together with several coregulator proteins stimulates the transcriptional activity that precedes a protein synthesis (Klinge, 2001; Nelson and

Habibi, 2013). Therefore, the implications of the biological relevance regarding the binding effects must be verified in vivo, in order to elucidate the processes mechanistically related (Costache et al., 2005), as well as the interactions with other molecules (Casals-Casas et al., 2008). Vitellogenin (VTG), a precursor protein of egg yolk, codified by a gene found to be regulated by ERE in fish (Teo et al., 1998), has been commonly used for in vivo detection of xenoestrogens. VTG gene is normally expressed in mature females only. VTG synthesis in adult males or immature fish is a well-known biomarker of estrogenic ED (Cheek et al., 2001; Knoebel et al., 2004; Rose et al., 2002; Tyler et al., 1999).

One of the most studied suspected xenoestrogens is Bisphenol A (BPA), a synthetic compound with multiple applications in industry, as a monomer for the production of polycarbonate and epoxy resins, including coatings for food and beverage cans, or as a component of

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adhesives, composites and electronic circuits (Gallart-Ayala et al., 2010). As a consequence of its versatility, BPA is globally distributed, and can be found in aquatic environments, including marine waters, with maximum concentrations frequently between 0.1 and > 10 µg/L (Lu et al., 2020; Salgueiro-González et al., 2019).

The ecotoxicological status of BPA is under strong debate. In the EU it can be used as additive in food-contact plastics, but with a specific migration limit of 0.6 mg kg⁻¹ (EC, 2011), and its use is restricted in infant plastic feeding bottles and toy manufacture (EU, 2014, 2011). Despite concerns on effects on human health (Environment Canada, 2013), the European Food Safety Authority has recently concluded BPA poses no health risk to humans because current exposure to this compound via ingestion is too low to cause damage (EFSA, 2015), whereas the European Chemicals Agency classified it as a substance of very high concern because of its toxicity for reproduction (ECHA, 2018).

According to in vitro tests with recombinant yeast and cell cultures, BPA is a weak transcriptional activator of nuclear ERs with a binding affinity of ca. 0.004% that of estradiol (Morohoshi et al., 2005). In vivo testing showed VTG induction in fish at BPA concentrations ranging from 5 to 500 µg/L (Flint et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2014), and the proteome of zebrafish embryos showed alterations associated with developmental and metabolic disorders upon exposure to 10 µg/L BPA (Dong et al., 2018). Chronic toxicity tests, including multigeneration tests, found ecologically relevant effects (impaired larval development, disrupted gonad development, reduced fecundity) at concentrations from 370 to 600 µg/L for invertebrates (Mihaich et al., 2018; Tato et al., 2018), and from 50 to 4000 in fish (Martínez et al., 2018; Mihaich et al., 2018; Staples et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2014). Those concentrations have very low likelihood to be found in aquatic environments for long periods (Staples et al., 2011; Yokota et al., 2000). Moreover, other studies report no effects on early development, fecundity or fertility of medaka until BPA concentrations as high as 1820 and 3120 µg/L (Kang et al., 2002; Yokota et al., 2000) and concluded that BPA has no adverse effects on reproductive success for this species. The mechanism of BPA toxicity in fish is supposed to involve the upregulation of genes whose expression is controlled by ERE such as the VTG (see above) and zona pellucida (ZP), and these genes are broadly used as biomarkers of xenoestrogen exposure.

Fish can metabolize BPA through several pathways that involve enzymes from the cytochrome P450 family and uridine 5'-diphosphoglucuronosyltransferases (UGT) - (Villeneuve et al., 2012). The increase of mRNA level of UGT, and their enzymatic activity described in embryos of *Oryzias melastigma* as well as the simultaneous increase of the BPA-glucuronide metabolite indicates that the main biotransformation pathway for BPA in fish leads to glucuronate forms, which lack estrogenic effects (Huang et al., 2018). However, oxidative metabolism of BPA leads to ED-active metabolites, such as 4-methyl-2,4-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)pent-1-ene (MBP), as demonstrated in rat hepatocytes (Yoshihara et al., 2004). The specific conditions for production of this metabolite are still unclear.

If the studies of BPA effects relative to fish are limited, those focused on marine fish are even less common (Maradonna et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2016), probably due to the complications that derive from maintaining marine cultures. To the best of our knowledge, no studies that evaluate the MBP effects in marine fish are present in the literature, and only a few freshwater-based studies are available (Brown et al., 2018; Ishibashi et al., 2005; Yamaguchi et al., 2005). The marine fish *Cyprinodon variegatus*, meets the requirements to be a practical ecotoxicological model, due to its reduced size, easy handling, short live cycle reproducible in captivity and, at molecular level, because of the genomic and proteomic information available (Warren and Nacci, 2014). The potential of omics technologies applied to this and other similar species to explore multiple adverse outcome pathways and novel biomarker discovery provides a solid background for this work (Knoebel et al., 2004; Martyniuk et al., 2020; Walker et al., 2007).

The aim of this study is to increase the understanding on the mode of

action of the estrogenic effects reported for BPA in fish, and the involvement of the BPA metabolite MBP. With this aim, we hypothesize that the liver proteomic profile in adult males of *C. variegatus* should present identifiable differences among BPA-exposed, MBP-exposed and non-exposed individuals. These differences in the whole proteome described through general alterations in biological processes and molecular functions should shed light on the mechanisms of estrogenic ED, whereas modifications on the levels of specific proteins could establish novel biomarkers valuable to detect xenoestrogen exposure.

2. Methods

2.1. Fish exposure

Adult males of *C. variegatus* with a weight and size of 1.57 ± 0.58 g and 4.34 ± 0.32 cm respectively were supplied by ECIMAT (CIM, University of Vigo). Fish were exposed for 7 days to waterborne bisphenol A (BPA) (CAS 80-05-7) and 4-methyl-2,4-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)pent-1-ene (MBP) (CAS 13464-24-9). Treatments were 10 µg/L of BPA, 10 µg/L of MBP, and solvent control (SC). Stock solutions were prepared using dimethylsulfoxide as carrier at a final concentration of 0.001% v/v. in all treatments. One-week acclimatization to exposure conditions was allowed before testing. With that aim 45 fish (15 per treatment) were individually transferred into 1.8L glass vessels, with continuous aeration, 16:8h light:dark photoperiod, daily food supply (Gemma Diamond 1.0 pellets, Skretting, France) and 90% water renewal daily. Salinity was set to 25 ± 0.2 by diluting pore size filtered seawater with distilled water; pH was 7.94 ± 0.03, dissolved oxygen was 7.48 ± 0.07 g/L, and temperature 18.8 ± 0.2 °C. All procedures and handling were done in compliance with EU animal welfare legislation, under the approval of the Ethical Committee for Animal Testing of University of Vigo (code ES360570181401).

2.2. Fish sampling, protein extraction and quantification

To obtain liver tissue samples, fish were euthanized with phenoxethanol (Merck KGaA, Germany) at the end of the exposure period, liver was dissected, weighted (mean = 0.024 ± 0.09g) and flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen.

Protein extraction and total quantification procedures were performed as described in Diz & Sánchez-Marín (2021) with minor modifications. Briefly, ultrasonic homogenization pulses (six pulses of 5 s spaced 30 s apart at 20% of amplitude, on ice) were applied to the samples immersed in lysis buffer (7M urea; 2M thiourea; 4% CHAPS). The supernatants obtained after centrifugation (20.913×g, 60 min at 4 °C) were collected and used for the total protein quantification and the future protein identification and quantification by mass spectrometry analysis. The total protein quantification was done following the modified version of the Bradford method (Ramagli and Rodriguez, 1985), adapted to microplates.

2.3. Isobaric labelling and fractionation of protein samples

Five pools per treatment were made, each one consisting of a mix of three independent samples, thus each pool can work as a biological replica. In each pool the total amount of proteins was kept balanced adding 35 µg of each constituent sample and the final concentration was adjusted to 0.5 µg/L. Pooling strategy was chosen to improve the statistical power, gaining the representativeness of more biological replicates while adhering to the limitation of the 10-plex isobaric labeling configuration (Diz et al., 2009).

Proteins were acetone precipitated, according to Tandem Mass Tag (TMT) 10-plex manual guidelines (Thermo Scientific; Pub No. MAN0016969) and with minor modifications described in Diz & Sánchez-Marín (2021), which consisted of adding 600 µL of pre-chilled acetone to 100 µL of each sample. After 2 h at -20 °C, samples were

centrifuged (two rounds at 8000g, 15 min at 4 °C), keeping the pellet. Proteins were resuspended in 100 µL of trimethylammonium bicarbonate 100 mM and treated with 5 µL of tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine 200 mM at 55 °C, to reduce cysteine residues. An alkylation with 5 µL of iodoacetamide 375 mM was done followed by a trypsin digestion, consisting of adding 10 µL of 0.1 µg/µL sequencing grade modified trypsin (Promega, Madison, WI).

Amine-reactive TMT 10-plex reagents (Thermo Scientific) were used for peptide isobaric labelling, allowing the formation of a master pool of ten biological replicates-pools. In the present study two independent 10-plex experiments were run, therefore, two master pools, each one to test the effects of each treatment, (BPA and MBP) versus the SC. Both experiments were structured as follow: the first was filled with 5 pools of SC samples and 5 pools of BPA samples. The second included the same 5 pools of SC used in the other TMT experiment and 5 pools of MBP samples. Notice that SC samples were the same used in both TMT 10-plex experiments in order to improve the capacity of comparison between experiments.

The procedure of fractioning the master pools and the electrospray ionization mass spectrometry analysis (ESI-MS/MS) that followed the isobaric labeling were carried out independently for each of the two 10-plex experiments and following the methodology of Sánchez-Marín et al. (2021).

2.4. Protein identification and quantification

MS/MS spectra comparison was performed against a *C. variegatus* proteome database (31881 protein sequences) downloaded from UniProt portal (September 6th, 2019), plus a set of common contaminants (cRAP protein sequences downloaded from <https://www.thegpm.org>), using the software PEAKS Studio v8.0 (Bioinformatics Solutions Inc., Waterloo, Canada). Precursor and fragment ion tolerance were set as 10 ppm and 0.02 Da respectively. A maximum of one missed trypsin cleavage site was allowed and the modifications of carbamidomethylation of cysteine and TMT 10-plex (N-terminal, K) were set as fixed while methionine oxidation was set as variable modifications. False discovery rate was obtained through the matches of spectra against decoy sequences and was set at 1% and 8.5% at peptide spectrum matches and protein level respectively. Peptide intensities obtained from the reporter ions of TMT mass tags were normalized based on the total sum of intensities within channel in relation to the reference channel. For protein quantification the requirements of containing a unique peptide and an ion intensity higher than 1×10^2 were established. The mass spectrometry proteomics data have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium via the PRIDE (Perez-Riverol et al., 2019) partner repository with the dataset identifier PXD029244 and 10.6019/PXD029244.

The nomenclature of VTG isoforms was based on the comparison of our unnamed sequences with sequences from Actinopterygii species annotated manually by Finn & Kristoffersen (2007). For the comparison, a phylogenetic tree was done (see below).

2.5. Statistical analysis of protein abundance data

For both TMT 10-plex experiments (BPA and MBP) the normalized values of protein abundance were used to detect statistically significant differences between the treatment (BPA or MBP) and the SC. A Student's t-test was performed for each quantified protein, applying the logarithmic transformation to the abundance and fixing the significance level at 5% (p-value 0.05). Multiple hypothesis testing problem was corrected by applying the SGoF correction using the SGoF software (Carvajal-Rodríguez et al., 2009) as discussed in Diz et al. (2011). Q-value was obtained (by SGoF software) and used as a complementary statistical indicator.

An identification of the gene ontology (GO) terms enriched by the treatments was done performing a functional annotation for all identified proteins, followed by an enrichment analysis based on Fisher exact

test (FDR = 0.05). The proteins whose levels in treated animals were statistically different from control were used as test set, whereas the total set of quantified proteins was the reference set.

3. Results

3.1. BPA exposure effects

The liver proteome profile of BPA-exposed *C. variegatus* adult males showed 21,325 peptide sequences, from which 3013 protein groups (hereafter referred simply as proteins) were identified and quantified. 81 of these proteins present statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in abundance compared to those found in the SC samples (complete data in [supplementary material S1](#)). However, after applying the SGoF multitest correction, no proteins remain statistically significant. A representation of the fold change (FC) and p-values of the proteins identified in the BPA treatment is shown in Fig. 1a.

3.2. MBP exposure effects

The liver proteome profile from the MBP-exposed adult males is composed by 24,360 peptide sequences, from which 2711 proteins could be identified; 2519 of them were common to those identified in the BPA-exposed fish. The similar, but not exact, number of proteins found in both experiments is explained by the batch-to-batch variation. Notice that although the SC samples were the same, they are independent 10-plex experiments. The results of the abundance comparison between MBP and SC for each protein (p-values and FC) are shown in Fig. 1b. From this comparison, 595 of the proteins showed statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in abundance compared to SC. After applying SGoF correction, 437 proteins remained significantly affected (complete data in [supplementary material S2](#)). The positive false discovery rate at the threshold fixed by the SGoF correction presents a q-value of 0.084.

3.2.1. Enrichment analysis

Four biological processes and five molecular functions are enriched in the MBP-affected protein set (test set) when compared to the whole quantified protein set (reference set) (Fig. 2). Most of these results are related with ribosomal structure and activity, *vid.* the ribosomal small subunit assembly process (GO:0000028), the maturation of small subunit rRNA from tricistronic rRNA transcript process (GO:0000462) and the molecular functions of structural constituents of ribosome (GO:0003735), large ribosomal subunit rRNA binding (GO:0070180) and the 7S RNA binding (GO:0008312). However, the enrichment analysis also reports alterations related with the synthesis of novel proteins and its transport. Specifically, the cytoplasmic translation process (GO:0002181), the SRP-dependent cotranslational protein targeting to membrane process (GO:0006614), and the molecular functions of mRNA binding (GO:0003729) and signal recognition particle binding (GO:0005047).

To broaden understanding of the effects of MBP in the ribosome activity, in parallel to the enrichment analysis, all the quantified ribosome-related proteins (a total of 57) have been extracted and analyzed (Table 1), 52 of which present a significant up-regulation in the MBP treatment (FC 2.07–1.22).

3.2.2. Estrogenic endocrine disruption

With the aim to identify if MBP causes estrogenic ED in *C. variegatus*, proteins involved in three ED-related biological processes have been extracted from the results: response to estrogen (GO:0043627), response to estradiol (GO:0032355), and cellular response to estrogen stimulus (GO:0071391). Seventeen ED-related proteins included in these three biological processes show significant differences in abundance in the MBP treatment (Table 2). The diversity of these proteins, strongly suggest that different signaling pathways are affected. ERE regulation could be the main mechanism that explains the alterations in these proteins.

Fig. 1. Volcano plot for liver quantified proteins from a) BPA-exposed and b) MBP-exposed fish. Green and red dots represent proteins significantly downregulated and upregulated, respectively, compared to solvent control after SGoF correction. Notice that no significantly affected proteins were found in the BPA treatment. Horizontal line represents a p-value threshold of 0.05, at logarithmic scale ($-\log_{10} p$). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Bar chart for GO terms, molecular functions (top) and biological processes (bottom), enriched in the set of MBP significantly affected proteins when compared with the reference set (all quantified proteins of the MBP TMT10-plex experiment). General terms if there are more specific terms related, are not shown, vid. The more general term “structural molecular activity” (not shown) and the specific “structural constituent of ribosome”. For each enriched GO term, the percentage of sequences from the affected protein set (blue) and the reference set (red) are shown. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Therefore, a list of proteins modulated by ERE has been selected from [Klinge \(2001\)](#), using the corresponding *C. variegatus* orthologs, due to the lack of studies based on this species. [Table 3](#) lists those ERE-regulated proteins.

VTG, present in two isoforms, VTGAb and VTGC, showed the strongest up-regulation (9-14 FC) of the ERE-regulated proteins in the presence of MBP. Other sequences related to VTG have also been

detected through the MS/MS analysis, such the VTG domain-containing protein or the Von Willebrand factor D domain-containing protein, founded upregulated with similar FC to complete VTG proteins. ZP, another protein involved in egg formation, related to sperm binding and formation of fertilization membrane, also showed a strong up-regulation (4-11 FC). This protein has been found in three isoforms in this experiment: ZP1, ZP3, ZP4.

Table 1

Ribosome-related proteins found in MBP experiment. "Accession" column points to the corresponding accession number from Uniprot; Protein names are set from Uniprot-TREMBL; FC is the fold-change when MBP exposure (10 µg/L) and solvent control abundance are compared. "p" and "q" indicate the p-values and q-values from the protein abundance t-test when comparing MBP treatment and solvent control. In grey no significant proteins (after SGoF correction).

Accession	Protein name	FC	p	q
A0A3Q2D335	60S ribosomal protein L27a	1.49	1.23E-05	0.001
A0A3Q2EC37	60S ribosomal protein L6	1.67	1.78E-05	0.001
A0A3Q2FT16	40S ribosomal protein S6	1.62	2.18E-05	0.001
A0A3Q2FWB5	S10_pectin domain-containing protein	1.42	2.44E-05	0.001
A0A3Q2D4U5	TRASH domain-containing protein	1.85	2.62E-05	0.001
A0A3Q2CN15	Ribosomal_S7 domain-containing protein	1.29	2.63E-05	0.001
A0A3Q2GHB8	60S ribosomal protein L13a	1.64	2.73E-05	0.001
A0A3Q2GKV8	Uncharacterized protein	2.00	2.91E-05	0.001
A0A3Q2E1S8	Ribosomal_L16 domain-containing protein	1.50	5.94E-05	0.002
A0A3Q2C6W4	40S ribosomal protein S26	1.37	6.07E-05	0.002
A0A3Q2DY75	DNA-(apurinic or apyrimidinic site) lyase	1.30	6.14E-05	0.002
A0A3Q2CW15	Ribosomal protein L15	1.89	7.11E-05	0.002
A0A3Q2DED9	60S ribosomal protein L18a	1.79	7.57E-05	0.002
A0A3Q2D6G0	60S ribosomal protein L34	2.07	8.55E-05	0.002
A0A3Q2EBC2	Uncharacterized protein	1.47	9.64E-05	0.003
A0A3Q2GKK8	Uncharacterized protein	1.33	1.06E-04	0.003
A0A3Q2CMU1	Ribosomal_L18e/L15P domain-containing protein	1.51	1.12E-04	0.003
A0A3Q2D2B5	40S ribosomal protein S13	1.42	1.21E-04	0.003
A0A3Q2G7M4	60S ribosomal protein L35a	1.65	1.35E-04	0.003
A0A3Q2G9R7	40S ribosomal protein S2	1.43	1.37E-04	0.003
A0A3Q2DBU0	40S ribosomal protein S3a	1.29	1.38E-04	0.003
A0A3Q2E8Q3	60S ribosomal protein L7a	1.66	1.54E-04	0.003
A0A3Q2GL56	60S ribosomal protein L8	1.56	1.60E-04	0.003
A0A3Q2EBP2	40S ribosomal protein S8	1.43	1.80E-04	0.004
A0A3Q2ECP7	Rib_recp_KP_reg domain-containing protein	1.56	1.82E-04	0.004
A0A3Q2FMP9	40S ribosomal protein S9	1.52	2.08E-04	0.004
A0A3Q2EAQ2	40S ribosomal protein S19	1.42	2.22E-04	0.004
A0A3Q2CY17	KOW domain-containing protein	1.57	2.23E-04	0.004
A0A3Q2CX18	Uncharacterized protein	1.44	2.30E-04	0.004
A0A3Q2DBU5	40S ribosomal protein S14*	1.30	2.35E-04	0.004
A0A3Q2DKE8	60S ribosomal protein L28	1.65	3.25E-04	0.005
A0A3Q2D712	60S ribosomal protein L35	1.55	3.41E-04	0.006
A0A3Q2FY37	Uncharacterized protein	1.77	4.26E-04	0.007
A0A3Q2CH23	Ribosomal protein	1.38	4.54E-04	0.007
A0A3Q2DTL6		1.44		0.007

Table 1 (continued)

Accession	Protein name	FC	p	q
A0A3Q2DCX1	RibosomalL4_associated_C domain-containing protein	1.57	4.58E-04	0.007
A0A3Q2CRE4	60S ribosomal protein L13	1.58	4.72E-04	0.007
A0A3Q2CZ94	Uncharacterized protein	1.41	5.13E-04	0.008
A0A3Q2D2Q8	40S ribosomal protein S11	1.46	6.02E-04	0.009
A0A3Q2EGA5	60S ribosomal protein L27	1.45	7.19E-04	0.009
A0A3Q2CY09	60S ribosomal protein L38	1.34	7.23E-04	0.010
A0A3Q2FKB4	40S ribosomal protein S4	1.37	8.35E-04	0.010
A0A3Q2DRY6	60S ribosomal protein L23	1.33	8.95E-04	0.010
A0A3Q2CSD2	40S ribosomal protein S17	1.26	8.99E-04	0.010
A0A3Q2EJW1	40S ribosomal protein S18	1.22	0.0013	0.013
A0A3Q2E6W8	60S ribosomal protein L12	1.24	0.0020	0.018
A0A3Q2DLH5	60S ribosomal protein L31	1.24	0.0024	0.021
A0A3Q2EK31	60S ribosomal protein L14	1.69	0.0029	0.024
A0A3Q2DZU3	60S ribosomal protein L30	1.31	0.0030	0.024
A0A3Q2G6W4	40S ribosomal protein S25	1.27	0.0032	0.025
A0A3Q2DCA4	Ribosomal protein L37	1.67	0.0053	0.034
A0A3Q2CLZ0	40S ribosomal protein S15a	1.32	0.0067	0.037
A0A3Q2EI00	60S ribosomal protein L21	1.27	0.0074	0.039
A0A3Q2CF63	Uncharacterized protein	1.16	0.0517	
A0A3Q2E1M9	Ribosomal_L18_c domain-containing protein	1.10	0.0716	
A0A3Q2GPC0	40S ribosomal protein S17	1.27	0.0868	
A0A3Q2EK67	40S ribosomal protein S20	1.11	0.1307	
	Ribosomal protein S5	1.12	0.1773	

Table 2

Proteins involved in the biological processes of response to estrogen (GO:0043627), response to estradiol (GO:0032355), and cellular response to estrogen stimulus (GO:0071391) affected by MBP. Protein names are obtained from different sources; Uniprot ^a, This study ^b, or NCBI ^c. VWFD: Von Willebrand factor D. SERPIN: Serine protease inhibitor. Other symbols as in Table 1.

Accession	Protein name	FC	p	q
A0A3Q2FF28	Vitellogenin domain-containing protein ^a	14.19	2.63E-06	2.04E-08
A0A3Q2DNR5	VWFD domain-containing protein ^a	7.80	9.79E-05	3.78E-07
A0A3Q2GA16	Vitellogenin Ab ^b	8.51	0.0001	1.98E-06
A0A3Q2FKW4	Pentaxin ^a	0.43	0.0001	0.003
A0A3Q2DQU0	VWFD domain-containing protein ^a	2.99	0.0002	0.004
A0A3Q2DFV0	Fibrinopeptide A ^a	0.67	0.0011	0.012
A0A3Q2EAS2	Complement C3-like ^c	0.65	0.0011	0.012
A0A3Q2DD15	Uncharacterized protein ^a	0.84	0.0013	0.013
A0A3Q2E811	Uncharacterized protein ^a	0.69	0.0046	0.031
A0A3Q2EEA2	Catalase ^b	0.82	0.0057	0.035
A0A3Q2D4E9	Uncharacterized protein ^a	0.85	0.0083	0.042
A0A3Q2D9W6	Uncharacterized protein ^a	0.52	0.013	0.058
A0A3Q2EKZ4	Signal transducer and activator of transcription ^a	0.81	0.017	0.068
A0A3Q2FJJ5	SERPIN domain-containing protein ^a	0.68	0.029	0.094
A0A3Q2D9J1	Uncharacterized protein ^a	0.88	0.030	0.096
A0A3Q2CE82	Aldo keto reductase D1 ^a	0.86	0.035	0.107
A0A3Q2CRX8	Uncharacterized protein ^a	0.85	0.038	0.112

Heat Shock Proteins 70 (HSP70) and hypoxia upregulated protein 1, other proteins regulated by an ERE, have been found among the identifications. Three of them are significantly upregulated in the presence of MBP, 1.4 to 1.7 FC.

Other protein related with an ERE and upregulated after the MBP exposure is the Cathepsin E (FC = 7.28). Complement C3 and the

Table 3

Proteins affected by MBP treatment found in this study whose genes are regulated by an estrogen responsive element. Symbols as in Table 2.

Accession	Protein name	FC	p	q
A0A3Q2FF28	Vitellogenin domain-containing protein ^a	14.19	2.63E-11	2.04E-08
A0A3Q2CDM8	Vitellogenin C ^b	9.91	6.25E-09	1.38E-06
A0A3Q2GA16	Vitellogenin Ab ^b	8.51	1.03E-08	1.98E-06
A0A3Q2DNR5	VWFD domain-containing protein ^a	7.81	9.79E-10	3.78E-07
A0A3Q2DQU0	VWFD domain-containing protein ^a	2.99	1.94E-04	3.89E-03
A0A3Q2FKU6	Zona pellucida 1 ^b	10.94	2.21E-09	6.82E-07
A0A3Q2E2H1	Zona pellucida 4 ^b	6.75	2.68E-10	1.38E-07
A0A3Q2E210	Zona pellucida 3 ^b	4.03	2.78E-08	4.78E-06
A0A3Q2DE82	Cathepsin E-like ^a	7.28	2.64E-11	2.04E-08
A0A3Q2DBG4	Heat shock 70 kDa protein 13 ^a	1.71	0.0067	0.037
A0A3Q2EDD4	Heat shock protein 70 family protein 5 ^a	1.45	0.00070	0.009
A0A3Q2FCG5	Hypoxia up-regulated protein 1 ^c	1.35	0.00059	0.008
A0A3Q2CZ23	Carnitine acyltransferase domain-containing prot ^a	0.79	0.0020	0.018
A0A3Q2EAS2	Complement C3-like ^c	0.65	0.0011	0.012

Carnitine acyltransferase domain protein, homologous to Cathepsin D in mammals are found downregulated after MBP exposure (FC = 0.65 and 0.79 respectively), both are also modulated by an ERE. Complement C3 presents an endopeptidase inhibitor activity while Cathepsin E and D are peptidases.

3.2.3. Peptidases and endopeptidase inhibitor activity

MBP exposure showed a remarkable and unexpected effect on a

Table 4

Peptidases (a) and proteins with endopeptidase inhibitor activity (b) found affected by MBP treatment. Symbols as in Table 1.

Accession	Protein name	FC	p	q
<i>a) Endopeptidase inhibitor activity</i>				
A0A3Q2D010	Whey acidic protein-like ^c	68.22	3.76E-05	9.67E-07
A0A3Q2EAS2	Complement C3-like ^c	0.65	0.0011	0.012
A0A3Q2ECL5	Zgc:112265 ^a	0.66	0.0056	0.035
A0A3Q2EBV8	A2M_N_2 domain-containing protein ^a	0.67	0.023	0.083
<i>b) Peptidases</i>				
A0A3Q2DE82	Cathepsin E-like ^a	7.28	2.64E-11	2.04E-08
A0A3Q2CL01	Protein disulfide-isomerase A4 ^a	2.56	2.08E-07	2.93E-05
A0A3Q2CUV2	Cystathionine gamma-lyase ^a	0.77	0.000481	0.007
A0A3Q2D697	Plasminogen ^a	0.54	0.00052	0.007
A0A3Q2DE64	Pyrraline-5-carboxylate reductase ^a	5.89	0.0025	0.021
A0A3Q2D6F7	Dual specificity mitogen-activated protein kinase 6 ^a	0.71	0.0036	0.026
A0A3Q2D8C9	Mitogen-activated protein kinase 2 ^a	0.84	0.0058	0.035
A0A3Q2EGF4	Protein kinase cAMP-dependent type I regulatory subunit alpha ^a	0.82	0.010	0.050
A0A3Q2DLC3	Serine/threonine kinase 38 ^a	0.70	0.011	0.051
A0A3Q2D461	Inactive tyrosine-protein kinase 7-like ^a	0.70	0.016	0.064
A0A3Q2CDE8	Putative aminopeptidase W07G4.4 ^a	0.85	0.017	0.070
A0A3Q2DW28	Macrophage stimulating 1 ^a	0.80	0.019	0.073

group of proteins with endopeptidase inhibitor activity. A total of four proteins with this molecular function are significantly affected (Table 4a). Among them stands out the most affected protein in this study, the Whey acidic protein (WAP), which shows a remarkable overexpression (FC = 68.22, p = 3.76E-05). In mammals, WAP is related to proliferation of mammary epithelial cells. In fact, this protein is homogeneously present in all MBP-treatment pools but absent from 4 of the five SC pools.

In contrast, a relevant number of peptidases altered by MBP exposure has been detected (Table 4b). It is noticeable that among the 12 peptidases inhibited, 5 of those have protein kinase activity: the dual specificity mitogen-activated protein kinase 6, the mitogen-activated protein kinase 2, the cAMP-dependent protein kinase type I-alpha regulatory subunit, and the serine/threonine-protein kinase 38.

4. Discussion

4.1. Role of proteomics in the detection of estrogenic endocrine disruption

Despite consensus based on in vitro tests classifying BPA as a weak transcriptional activator of nuclear ERs, and thus as a potential xenoestrogen, there is a lack of agreement on the environmental relevance of these findings. In vivo evidence using different fish species found threshold of effects spanning more than four orders of magnitude (Dong et al., 2018; Flint et al., 2012; Martinez et al., 2018; Mihaich et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2014). Key signaling pathways commonly affected by xenoestrogens are those regulated by nuclear ER, which promote the synthesis of several proteins controlled by ERE (Gruber et al., 2004), such as the VTG, broadly used as biomarker of xenoestrogen exposure. Besides this mechanism, other fast, non-genomic, signaling cascades have been described to be triggered by xenoestrogens, as the pathway mediated by the membrane-bound ER (Kiyama and Wada-Kiyama, 2015). Moreover, alterations caused by xenoestrogens not only affect isolated biomarkers, but also extend along interconnected metabolic pathways, leading to widespread effects and a distinctive pattern of proteome alteration. At this point, high-throughput (shotgun) proteomic analysis acquires relevance in ecotoxicology, since it allows tracking alterations through the theoretically complete set of proteins in a tissue, organ, or organism by directly quantifying protein abundance. Although proteomics have not received so far the same attention as other omic-based techniques (Liang et al., 2020), the study at protein level yields physiologically-relevant functional information that cannot be obtained otherwise (Silvestre et al., 2012), as illustrated by the lack of correlation observed between mRNA and proteins (Diz and Calvete, 2016; Vogel and Marcotte, 2012).

4.2. Potential involvement of MBP in the mode of action of BPA

In this study an exposure to 10 µg/L BPA, a concentration similar to maximum concentrations reported in aquatic environments (reviewed by Flint et al., 2012) for 7 days did not cause detectable effects over the liver proteome of *C. variegatus* males (see Fig. 1). In contrast, the same exposure to the BPA metabolite, MBP, caused widespread changes in the liver proteome, including effects typical of exposure to estrogens (see Section 4.3). Bacterial biotransformation of BPA in aerobic media includes a first step of ipso-hydroxylation by a monooxygenase followed by a cleavage of the carbon-phenyl bond (Kolvenbach et al., 2007). Using ¹⁴C-labeled BPA Kolvenbach et al. (2007) described 4-isopropylphenol and 4-isopropenylphenol as metabolites resulting from the cleavage of the hydroxylated BPA. In mammals the same oxidative route has been reported in vitro in the presence of liver microsomes, cytochrome P450-3A isozymes and NADPH (Nakamura et al., 2011). Recombination of those BPA fragments is hypothesized as the mechanism of formation of the ED-active metabolite MBP (Yoshihara et al., 2004; Gramerc Skledar et al., 2016). MBP formation in vitro requires the cellular machinery present in both cytosolic and microsomal fractions of rat hepatocytes,

including the NADPH generating system (Okuda et al., 2011; Yoshihara et al., 2004). Since this cellular machinery is also present in fish hepatocytes, the potential metabolic activation of BPA by this mechanism is also expected in fish. In fact, the increase in estrogenic potency of MBP compared to BPA found in vivo for fish (Ishibashi et al., 2005; Yamaguchi et al., 2005) and mammals (Okuda et al., 2010), was very similar: 300-fold and 500-fold, respectively. This comparatively low in vivo estrogenicity of BPA points at very limited formation of MBP in vertebrates or very efficient conjugation and consequent inactivation of oxidized metabolites, at least under the experimental conditions used in the studies available. Okuda et al. (2011) suggest that metabolic activation of BPA may be relevant only in biological systems where glucuronic conjugation is not efficient, such as phetal stages of mammals. On the other hand, metabolism of BPA by microbiota under very specific conditions that vary among studies may contribute to dissimilar results concerning BPA estrogenicity. Further research manipulating these conditions, and establishing links between MBP formation and ED effects, are needed in order to explore this issue.

As above discussed, a common mode of action for xenoestrogens is their interaction with the nuclear ERs. When discussing the differential estrogenicity of BPA metabolites, Okuda et al. (2011) remark that the flexible structure of the bridging moiety in an active metabolite may be essential to bind the ER, since a rigid-bridged but otherwise structurally similar metabolite resulted to be inactive. In silico studies about the affinity of BPA and MBP for the human ER using 3D-docking energy models predicted a low affinity of BPA, whereas the 3D structure of MBP showed key contacts that increased by 1000-fold its affinity for the ER (Baker and Chandsawangbhuwana, 2012), a figure similar to the 500-fold higher estrogenicity of MBP reported in mammals (Okuda et al., 2010).

4.3. Effects on proteins regulated by ERE

The overall effect on the 14 ERE-controlled proteins that showed significant alterations in the MBP treatment was a remarkable upregulation, excepting two proteins that were slightly downregulated (see Table 3). The most noticeable effects (FC values from 3 to 14) concern induction of VTG and ZP proteins, both synthesized naturally in the liver and ovary of female fish. This pattern of alterations caused by MBP is very similar to the characteristic pattern of endocrine disruption caused by exposure to ethinylestradiol (EE2) in the same species (Schönemann et al., submitted), where 10 of the 14 ERE-controlled proteins are affected in the same way and with a similar intensity. Both studies are fully comparable due to the consistency between methodologies, consisting of ESI-MS/MS shotgun liver proteome analysis complemented with a TMT 10-plex isobaric labelling.

Our results show an increase of VTG levels in the liver of *C. variegatus* males exposed to MBP, but not in those exposed to BPA. The major function of VTG is to transport lipids to the ovary/oocytes (Hussain et al., 2012). Studies using male medaka (*Oryzias latipes*) verified the responsiveness of VTG to the MBP, and established that the potency of the induction by MBP was ca. 300-fold higher than that by BPA (Ishibashi et al., 2005; Yamaguchi et al., 2005).

The exposure to MBP generates significant changes in the levels of expression of two VTG sequences; VTGAb and VTGC (Table 3). The higher response to MBP of the isoform VTGAb (A0A3Q2GA16) is in line with results reported by Yamaguchi et al. (2005), who found the same isoform (named VTG2 in their study) the most responsive to MBP. Freshwater fish, *Danio rerio*, exposed to a classical estrogenic ED, EE2, shows also alterations at the protein level of several VTG isoforms, where alterations are reported in VTG1 and VTG2 (Wit et al., 2010). VTG1 is not present in the *C. variegatus* proteome. The number and structure of VTG isoforms in fish are variable among species (Finn and Kristoffersen, 2007), which makes difficult to compare results among species and underlines the relevance of studying alterations at the isoform level, in order to elucidate the specific modes of action of

pollutants, and to select the more suitable forms to be used as biomarkers.

All ZP isoforms previously reported in fish (ZP1, ZP3, ZP4) (Litscher and Wassarman, 2018), playing roles in egg deposition, oogenesis, embryogenesis, egg protection and fertilization (Arukwe et al., 1997), are markedly upregulated in the MBP treatment, with ZP1 showing the greatest change (FC = 10.9). Maradonna et al. (2014) attributed the differential responsiveness to estrogenic substances of the ZP isoforms to the presence of different ERE-like regions in the promoter region of this gene.

4.4. WAP protein as a novel biomarker of xenoestrogen exposure

The highly significant ($p < 0.001$) and quantitatively remarkable (FC = 68.2) increment in the levels of a WAP-like protein (A0A3Q2D0I0) elicited by MBP exposure is the most conspicuous result of this study. In fact, the presence of this protein is not detectable in four of the five pooled samples belonging to the control group, whereas it is present homogeneously in all the MBP exposed samples. WAP are proteins broadly distributed in the animal kingdom, with various and dissimilar functions, being the most abundant protein of milk whey fraction (Simpson et al., 2000). In mammals, WAP levels change according to the lactation and menstrual cycle phases, and are regulated by the tissular amounts of estradiol and other hormones implicated in the reproductive process (Chen et al., 2016; Simpson et al., 2000), whereas in fish the role of WAP has not been determined. Since the pattern of alteration of the male liver proteome upon MBP exposure includes characteristics such as induction of VTG, ZP and other ERE-controlled proteins typical of estrogen exposure, we postulate the induction of WAP-like protein as a biomarker of exposure to estrogenic endocrine disrupting compounds in fish.

In mammals, WAP shows endopeptidase inhibitor activity; this is in line with previous studies that include this protein in the group of protease inhibitors, due to their amino acid sequence homology (Simpson et al., 2000). In the next section we will see that MBP exposure significantly altered a number of peptidases (Table 4). On that basis, we can speculate that WAP can play a role in the activation of a regulatory mechanism of the protease activity in fish, but this subject needs further research.

4.5. Peptidase alterations

Twelve peptidases are found affected by MBP treatment in the liver proteome of male *C. variegatus*, five of them presenting kinase activity (Table 4). The protein kinases are a diverse family, responsible for the protein activation/inactivation by phosphorylation dependent reversible modifications. Peptidases are a widely diverse group in terms of size, structure and subcellular localization (Taylor et al., 1992), and play a role in a multitude of cellular processes, including division, proliferation, apoptosis, and differentiation (Manning et al., 2002). Nine peptidases were moderately inhibited upon BPA exposure (FC ranging from 0.54 to 0.85). Williams et al. (2007) evidenced that BPA exposures causes inhibition of different peptidases, including the mitogen-activated protein kinase 2-associated protein 1r, which verify peptidases are sensitive to this kind of pollutants.

Conversely, three peptidases were induced, being Cathepsin E (A0A3Q2DE82), an aspartic proteinase of the same family that the pepsin and renin, the one that showed the highest upregulation (FC = 7.28). Cathepsins are localized in the lysosomal compartment that provides the acidic environment necessary to the accomplishment of their catalytic function. Their expression has been directly related to estrogen availability, being produced naturally in the female liver or in the liver of males exposed to estrogenic substances (Borrelli et al., 2006). Several cathepsins have been observed to play a role in the VTG degradation (Carnevali et al., 1999), and individual VTG domains have been found in this study upregulated by MBP treatment. This finding

suggests that VTG degradation is occurring under our experimental conditions. Bioinformatics data available on VTGC do not allow to make the difference between its origin, either as a protein isoform translated already as VTGC, or as a product of VTG degradation by cathepsin action such as the case of phosvitin, (Hara et al., 2016).

4.6. Implications for the choice of housekeeping genes in ED studies

The largest group of proteins affected by MBP exposure was composed by 52 proteins related with ribosomes (see Table 1), and all of them showed up-regulation patterns (intensity ranges between 1.22 and 2.07 FC). Only five ribosomal-related proteins have been found with no significant changes of abundance when they are compared to the control. The strongly consistent upregulation of these proteins supports the overall results obtained in the enrichment analysis, which point to the stimulation of protein synthesis and its transport as the main effect of MBP exposure.

Furthermore, the advances of omics field have allowed the identification of new and probably more sensitive biomarkers, as well as the verification of the classical ones. Nonetheless, the pronounced induction of ribosomal proteins by MBP allows us to alert about the use of some ribosomal proteins as housekeeping genes. For example, the ribosomal protein L13A (A0A3Q2GHB8), which has been used as a housekeeping gene for exposure to endocrine disruptors in fish (Dong et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2013), is significantly induced, and thus not suitable as reference gene in ED testing. Williams et al. (2007), also verified up-regulation of L13A (A0A3Q2G4B8) and L31 (A0A3Q2E6W8) after estradiol exposure in the European flounder (*Platichthys flesus*), reinforcing the estrogenic activity of MBP. Our results are in line with some previous findings questioning the use of ribosomal genes in transcriptomic analysis as reference genes for data normalization due to dependence on tissue and experimental conditions (Thorrez et al., 2008).

5. Conclusions

Environmentally relevant exposure to BPA (10 µg/L, for 7 days) caused no detectable effects over the liver proteome in *C. variegatus* males. In contrast, exposure to the BPA oxidative metabolite, MBP, at the same concentration and time prompted a profound change in the liver proteome profile similar to that caused by exposure to EE2, and thus characteristic of estrogenic endocrine disruption. This distinctive *in vivo* alteration of the proteome includes upregulation of ERE-mediated proteins, such as different forms of VTG and ZP (VTGAb, VTGC, ZP1, ZP3 and ZP4), as expected from the higher affinity of MBP to the ER predicted by *in vitro* and *in silico* studies. WAP displays the highest upregulation found in this study. This fact points at WAP as a novel biomarker for xenoestrogen exposure in marine fish.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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